

Yensen tengsizligi va uning tadbirlari.

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1.Kirish.

Ma'lumki tengsizliklar matematikada katta o'rin egallaydi. Biz ushbu maqolada tengsizliklarda katta o'rin tutgan Yensen tengsizligi haqida yozdik. Shuningdek Yensen tengsizligidan foydalanib bir nechta mashhur tengsizliklarni isbotlash va bir nechta misollarga tadbirini kiritdik. Bu maqola asosan matematika bilan shug'ullanuvchi va xalqaro olimpiadalarga tayyorlanuvchi o'quvchilar uchun mo'ljallangan. Biz daslab Yensen tengsizligiga kirishdan oldin biz uchun muhim bo'lgan funkiyaning qavariqligi haqida biroz ma'lumotlarni ko'rib chiqamiz.

2.Funksiyaning qavariqligi va botiqligi.

Faraz qilaylik $f(x)$ funksiya (a,b) intervalda berilgan bo'lib, $x_1, x_2 \in (a,b)$ uchun $x_1 < x_2$ bo'lsin.

$f(x)$ funksiya grafigining $(x_1, f(x_1)), (x_2, f(x_2))$ nuqtalaridan o'tuvchi to'g'ri chiziqni $y=l(x)$ quyidagicha

$$l(x) = \frac{x_2 - x}{x_2 - x_1} f(x_1) + \frac{x - x_1}{x_2 - x_1} f(x_2)$$

bo'ladi.

1-ta'rif. Agar har qanday oraliq $(x_1, x_2) \subset (a,b)$ intervalda joylashgan $\forall x \in (x_1, x_2)$ uchun

$$f(x) \leq l(x)$$

bo'lsa, $f(x)$ funksiya (a,b) intervalda quyidan qavariq funksiya deyiladi. Agar $f(x) < l(x)$ tengsizlik bajarilsa $f(x)$ funksiya (a,b) intervalda quyidan qat'iy qavariq funksiya deyiladi.

2-ta'rif. Agar har qanday oraliq $(x_1, x_2) \subset (a,b)$ intervalda joylashgan $\forall (x) \in (x_1, x_2)$ uchun

$$f(x) \geq l(x)$$

bo'lsa, $f(x)$ funksiya (a, b) intervalda yuqoridan qavariq funksiya deyiladi. Agar $f(x) > l(x)$ tengsizlik bajarilsa $f(x)$ funksiya (a, b) intervalda yuqoridan qat'iy qavariq funksiya deyiladi.

Funksiyaning quyidan va yuqoridan qavaraqligini quyidagicha ham ta'riflash ham mumkin.

Aytaylik, $\alpha_1 \geq 0, \alpha_2 \geq 0, \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 = 1$ bo'lib, $\forall x_1, x_2 \in (a, b)$ bo'lsin.

3-ta'rif. Agar

$$f(\alpha_1 x_1 + \alpha_2 x_2) \leq \alpha_1 f(x_1) + \alpha_2 f(x_2)$$

bo'lsa, $f(x)$ funksiya (a, b) intervalda quyidan qavariq funksiya deyiladi. Agar ishora qat'iy kichik bo'lsa, $f(x)$ funksiya (a, b) intervalda quyidan qat'iy qavariq funksiya deyiladi.

4-ta'rif. Agar

$$f(\alpha_1 x_1 + \alpha_2 x_2) \geq \alpha_1 f(x_1) + \alpha_2 f(x_2)$$

bo'lsa, $f(x)$ funksiya (a, b) intervalda yuqorida qavariq funksiya deyiladi. Agar ishora qat'iy katta bo'lsa, $f(x)$ funksiya (a, b) intervalda yuqoridan qat'iy qavariq funksiya deyiladi.

Endi bir nechta teoremani isbotsiz keltirib o'tamiz.

1-teorema. Faraz qilaylik, $f(x)$ funksiya (a, b) intervalda berilgan bo'lib, unda $f'(x)$ hosilaga ega bo'lsin. $f(x)$ funksiyaning (a, b) intervalda quyidan qavariq bo'lishi uchun $f'(x)$ ning (a, b) intervalda o'suvchi bo'lishi zarur va yetarli.

2-teorema. Faraz qilaylik, $f(x)$ funksiya (a, b) intervalda berilgan bo'lib, unda $f'(x)$ hosilaga ega bo'lsin. $f(x)$ funksiyaning (a, b) intervalda yuqoridan qavariq bo'lishi uchun $f'(x)$ ning (a, b) intervalda kamayuvchi bo'lishi zarur va yetarli.

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 7, 31 Июль

Aytaylik, $f(x)$ funksiya (a, b) intervalda berilgan bo'lib, u shu intervalda $f''(x)$ hosilaga ega bo'lsin. Bundan tashqari, (a, b) intervalning har qanay (α, β) ($(\alpha, \beta) \subset (a, b)$) qismida $f''(x)$ aynan nolga teng bo'lmasin.

3-teorema. $f(x)$ funksiyaning (a, b) intervalda quyidan qavariq bo'lishi uchun (a, b) intervalda $f''(x) \geq 0$ bo'lishi zarur va yetarli.

4-teorema. $f(x)$ funksiyaning (a, b) intervalda yuqoridan qavariq bo'lishi uchun (a, b) intervalda $f''(x) \leq 0$ bo'lishi zarur va yetarli.

Biz Yensen tengsizligini ko'rganimizda asosan 3 va 4-teoremalardan foydalanamiz.

3.Yensen tengsizligi.

Yensen tengsizligi. $f: (a, b) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ funsiya (a, b) intervalda quyidan qavariq bo'lsin. U holda $n \in \mathbb{N}$ barcha $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in (a, b)$ lar va $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \dots + \lambda_n = 1$ shartni qanoatlantiruvchi ixtiyoriy $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n \in (0, 1)$ sonlar uchun

$$f(\lambda_1 x_1 + \lambda_2 x_2 + \dots + \lambda_n x_n) \leq \lambda_1 f(x_1) + \lambda_2 f(x_2) + \dots + \lambda_n f(x_n)$$

tengsizlik o'rinli.

Isbot. Biz bu tengsizlikni isbotlashda induksiya metodidan foydalanamiz.

$n=1$ da $\lambda_1=1$ bo'ladi va $f(\lambda_1 x_1) = f(x_1)$ ekanligida biz $f(\lambda_1 x_1) = \lambda_1 f(x_1)$ tenglikka ega bo'lamiz. Shuning uchun tengsizlik o'rinli.

Agar $n=2$ bo'lsa tengsizlik qavariq funksiyaning ta'rifiga to'g'ri keladi.

Faraz qilaylik $n=k$ da barcha $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k \in (a, b)$ lar va $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \dots + \lambda_k = 1$ shartni qanoatlantiruvchi ixtiyoriy $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_k \in (0, 1)$ sonlar uchun

$$f(\lambda_1 x_1 + \lambda_2 x_2 + \dots + \lambda_k x_k) \leq \lambda_1 f(x_1) + \lambda_2 f(x_2) + \dots + \lambda_k f(x_k)$$

tengsizlik o'rinli bo'lsin.

$n = k + 1$ da barcha $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{k+1} \in (a, b)$ lar va $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \dots + \lambda_{k+1} = 1$ shartni qanoatlantiruvchi ixtiyoriy $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_{k+1} \in (0, 1)$ sonlar bo'lsin. U holda

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1 x_1 + \lambda_2 x_2 + \dots + \lambda_{k+1} x_{k+1} &= (\lambda_1 x_1 + \lambda_2 x_2 + \dots + \lambda_k x_k) + \lambda_{k+1} x_{k+1} = \\ &= (1 - \lambda_{k+1}) \left(\frac{\lambda_1}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} x_1 + \frac{\lambda_2}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} x_2 + \dots + \frac{\lambda_k}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} x_k \right) + \lambda_{k+1} x_{k+1} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Agar

$$y_{k+1} = \frac{\lambda_1}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} x_1 + \frac{\lambda_2}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} x_2 + \dots + \frac{\lambda_k}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} x_k$$

deb belgilasak. U holda $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k \in (a, b)$ ligidan

$$\begin{aligned} y_{k+1} &= \frac{\lambda_1}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} x_1 + \frac{\lambda_2}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} x_2 + \dots + \frac{\lambda_k}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} x_k \\ &> \frac{\lambda_1}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} a + \frac{\lambda_2}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} a + \dots + \frac{\lambda_k}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} a = \frac{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \dots + \lambda_k}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} a = a \end{aligned}$$

Shunga o'xshash $y_{k+1} < b$ ekanligi isbotlanadi. Demak $y_{k+1} \in (a, b)$ bo'ladi. Quyidan qavariq funksiya ta'rifi va (1) dan foydalansak, biz quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz.

$$\begin{aligned} f(\lambda_1 x_1 + \lambda_2 x_2 + \dots + \lambda_{k+1} x_{k+1}) &= f((1 - \lambda_{k+1}) y_{k+1} + \lambda_{k+1} x_{k+1}) \\ &\leq (1 - \lambda_{k+1}) f(y_{k+1}) + \lambda_{k+1} f(x_{k+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

bizga ma'lumki.

$$\frac{\lambda_1}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} + \frac{\lambda_2}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} + \dots + \frac{\lambda_k}{1 - \lambda_{k+1}} = 1$$

tenglik o'rinli. U holda

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 7, 31 Июль

$$\begin{aligned} f(y_{k+1}) &= f\left(\frac{\lambda_1}{1-\lambda_{k+1}}x_1 + \frac{\lambda_2}{1-\lambda_{k+1}}x_2 + \dots + \frac{\lambda_k}{1-\lambda_{k+1}}x_k\right) \\ &\leq \frac{\lambda_1}{1-\lambda_{k+1}}f(x_1) + \frac{\lambda_2}{1-\lambda_{k+1}}f(x_2) + \dots + \frac{\lambda_k}{1-\lambda_{k+1}}f(x_k) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

va ninoyat, (2) va (3) dan biz isbotlayotgan

$$f(\lambda_1x_1 + \lambda_2x_2 + \dots + \lambda_{k+1}x_{k+1}) \leq \lambda_1f(x_1) + \lambda_2f(x_2) + \dots + \lambda_{k+1}f(x_{k+1})$$

tengsizlik kelib chiqadi. Demak matematik induksiya metodidan foydalanib Yensen tengsizligi isbotlandi.

Eslatma. Agar f quyidan qavariq funksiya bo'lsa, Yensen tengsizligining tenglik holati faqat $x_1 = x_2 = \dots = x_n$ bo'lganda bajariladi.

Agar f funksiya yuqoridan qavariq bo'lsa, Yensen tengsizligida faqat tengsizlik ishorasi o'zgaradi. Ya'ni

$$f(\lambda_1x_1 + \lambda_2x_2 + \dots + \lambda_nx_n) \geq \lambda_1f(x_1) + \lambda_2f(x_2) + \dots + \lambda_nf(x_n)$$

Yensen tengsizligini yana quyidagich ham yozish mumkin.

Agar $f: I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ funsiya I da quyidan qavariq, $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in I$ va $m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n > 0$ shartni qanoatlantiruvchi $m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n \geq 0$ haqiqiy sonlar uchun

$$f\left(\frac{m_1x_1 + m_2x_2 + \dots + m_nx_n}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}\right) \leq \frac{m_1f(x_1) + m_2f(x_2) + \dots + m_nf(x_n)}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}$$

tengsizlik o'rinli.

4. Yensen tengsizligidan foydalanib mashhur tengsizliklarni isbotlash.

AM-GM tengsizligi. Agar $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ musbat haqiqiy sonlar uchun

$$\sqrt[n]{x_1x_2\dots x_n} \leq \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}$$

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 7, 31 Июль

Isbot. Agar $f(x) = -\ln x$ funsiya $(0, \infty)$ intervalda qaraylik. Bu funsiyaning 2-tartibli hosilasi $f''(x) = \frac{1}{x^2} > 0$ bo'ladi, demak $f(x)$ quyidan qa'tiy qavariq funksiya $(0, \infty)$ intervalda.

$\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \dots = \lambda_n = \frac{1}{n}$ va $x_i \in (0, \infty), i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ uchun Yensen tengsizligini qo'llaymiz.

$$-\ln\left(\frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}\right) \leq -\left(\frac{\ln(x_1) + \ln(x_2) + \dots + \ln(x_n)}{n}\right)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \frac{\ln(x_1) + \ln(x_2) + \dots + \ln(x_n)}{n} \leq \ln\left(\frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}\right)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \ln(x_1 x_2 \dots x_n)^{1/n} \leq \ln\left(\frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}\right)$$

bundan

$$\sqrt[n]{x_1 x_2 \dots x_n} \leq \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}$$

$AM - GM$ tengsizligi kelib chiqadi.

Teorema. (Koshi-Bunyokovskiy tengsizligi) Agar $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n; b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n$ haqiqiy sonlar uchun

$$(a_1 b_1 + a_2 b_2 + \dots + a_n b_n)^2 \leq (a_1^2 + a_2^2 + \dots + a_n^2)(b_1^2 + b_2^2 + \dots + b_n^2)$$

tengsizlik o'rinli va tenglik holati faqat va faqat $\frac{a_1}{b_1} = \frac{a_2}{b_2} = \dots = \frac{a_n}{b_n}$ bo'lganda bo'ladi.

Isbot. Agar $f(x) = x^2$ funksiyaning $\mathbb{R}$ sohada qarasaq. $f''(x) = 2 > 0$ bo'ladi. Ya'ni $f(x)$ funksiya quyidan qavariq bo'ladi. U holda Yensen tengsizligidan foydalansak

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 7, 31 Июль

$$f\left(\frac{m_1x_1 + m_2x_2 + \dots + m_nx_n}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}\right) \leq \frac{m_1f(x_1) + m_2f(x_2) + \dots + m_nf(x_n)}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}.$$

Biz quyidagini olamiz

$$\left(\frac{m_1x_1 + m_2x_2 + \dots + m_nx_n}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}\right)^2 \leq \frac{m_1x_1^2 + m_2x_2^2 + \dots + m_nx_n^2}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}$$

yoki

$$(m_1x_1 + m_2x_2 + \dots + m_nx_n)^2 \leq (m_1x_1^2 + m_2x_2^2 + \dots + m_nx_n^2)(m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n)$$

Agar $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ uchun $x_i = \frac{a_i}{b_i}$, $m_i = b_i^2$ deb belgilash kiritsak.

U holda biz quyidagi

$$(a_1b_1 + a_2b_2 + \dots + a_nb_n)^2 \leq (a_1^2 + a_2^2 + \dots + a_n^2)(b_1^2 + b_2^2 + \dots + b_n^2)$$

Koshi-Bunyakovskiy tengsizligiga ega bo'lamiz.

Teorema.(Gyuygens tengsizligi) Agar $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$ musbat haqiqiy sonlar uchun

$$(1 + a_1)(1 + a_2) \dots (1 + a_n) \geq (1 + \sqrt[n]{a_1a_2 \dots a_n})^n$$

tengsizlik o'rinli.

Isbot. Agar $f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $f(x) = \ln(1 + e^x)$ funksiyani qarasak. Barcha $x \in \mathbb{R}$ uchun $f''(x) = \frac{e^x}{(1 + e^x)^2} > 0$ tenglik o'rinli bo'ladi. Demak $f(x)$ funksiya quyidan qavariq bo'ladi. Yensen tengsizligidan foydalanamiz.

$$f\left(\frac{m_1x_1 + m_2x_2 + \dots + m_nx_n}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}\right) \leq \frac{m_1f(x_1) + m_2f(x_2) + \dots + m_nf(x_n)}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}.$$

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 7, 31 Июль

Agar $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ uchun $m_i = \frac{1}{n}$ va $x_i = \ln a_i$ deb almashtirish bajarsak,

$$f\left(\frac{\ln a_1 + \ln a_2 + \dots + \ln a_n}{n}\right) \leq \frac{f(\ln a_1) + f(\ln a_2) + \dots + f(\ln a_n)}{n}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \ln\left(1 + \exp\left(\frac{\ln a_1 a_2 \dots a_n}{n}\right)\right) \leq \frac{\ln(1 + a_1) + \ln(1 + a_2) + \dots + \ln(1 + a_n)}{n}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow n \ln(1 + \sqrt[n]{a_1 a_2 \dots a_n}) \leq \ln(1 + a_1)(1 + a_2) \dots (1 + a_n)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow (1 + a_1)(1 + a_2) \dots (1 + a_n) \geq (1 + \sqrt[n]{a_1 a_2 \dots a_n})^n$$

bu esa Gyuygens tengsizligi.

Teorema. (Yung tengsizligi) Agar $p, q > 1$ haqiqiy sonlar $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$ tenglikni

qanoatlantirsa. u holda ixtiyoriy $a, b > 0$ uchun $ab \leq \frac{a^p}{p} + \frac{b^q}{q}$ tengsizli o'rinli va

tenglik holati faqat va faqat $a^p = b^q$ bo'ladi.

Isbot. Agar $f(x) = e^x$ funksiyani $(0, \infty)$ sohada qarash $f''(x) = e^x > 0$ bo'ladi ixtiyoriy $x \in \mathbb{R}$. Demak $f(x)$ funksiya $(0, \infty)$ sohada quyidan qavariq. Yensen tengsizligidan $n = 2$ bo'lgan holdan foydalanamiz.

$$f\left(\frac{m_1 x_1 + m_2 x_2}{m_1 + m_2}\right) \leq \frac{m_1 f(x_1) + m_2 f(x_2)}{m_1 + m_2}$$

tengsizlikda $m_1 = \frac{1}{p}, m_2 = \frac{1}{q}, x_1 = p \ln a$ va $x_2 = q \ln b$ belgilask kiritsak.

$$f\left(\frac{x_1}{p} + \frac{x_2}{q}\right) \leq \frac{1}{p} f(x_1) + \frac{1}{q} f(x_2) \Leftrightarrow e^{\frac{x_1}{p} + \frac{x_2}{q}} \leq \frac{e^x}{p} + \frac{e^y}{q}$$

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 7, 31 Июль

$$\Leftrightarrow e^{\ln a + \ln b} \leq \frac{e^{p \ln a}}{p} + \frac{e^{q \ln b}}{q} \Leftrightarrow e^{\ln ab} \leq \frac{e^{\ln a^p}}{p} + \frac{e^{\ln b^q}}{q}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow ab \leq \frac{a^p}{p} + \frac{b^q}{q}$$

tengsizlikga ega bo'lamiz. Tenglik holati $x_1 = x_2$ bo'lganda, ya'ni, $a^p = b^q$ holda bo'ladi. Yung tengsizligi isbotlandi.

Teorema.(Gyolder tengsizligi) Agar $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n; b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n$ musbat haqiqiy sonlar va $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$ sharni qanoatlantiruvchi $p, q > 1$ sonlar uchun

$$\sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i \leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n b_i^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}$$

tengsizlik o'rinli va tenglik holati faqat va faqat $\frac{a_1^p}{b_1^q} = \frac{a_2^p}{b_2^q} = \dots = \frac{a_n^p}{b_n^q}$ da o'rinli.

Isbot. $f: \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, f(x) = x^p$ funsiya $p > 1$ uchun qaraymiz. $f(x)$ funsiya quyidan qavariq chunki $f''(x) = p(p-1)x^{p-2} > 0$ bo'ladi. U xolda Yensen tengsizligini qo'llasak.

$$f\left(\frac{m_1 x_1 + m_2 x_2 + \dots + m_n x_n}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}\right) \leq \frac{m_1 f(x_1) + m_2 f(x_2) + \dots + m_n f(x_n)}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}$$

$$\left(\frac{m_1 x_1 + m_2 x_2 + \dots + m_n x_n}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}\right)^p \leq \frac{m_1 x_1^p + m_2 x_2^p + \dots + m_n x_n^p}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}.$$

yoki

$$(m_1 x_1 + m_2 x_2 + \dots + m_n x_n)^p \leq (m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n)^{p-1} (m_1 x_1^p + m_2 x_2^p + \dots + m_n x_n^p)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow m_1 x_1 + m_2 x_2 + \dots + m_n x_n \leq (m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n)^{\frac{p-1}{p}} (m_1 x_1^p + m_2 x_2^p + \dots + m_n x_n^p)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 7, 31 Июль

$\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$ tenglikdan $\frac{p-1}{p} = \frac{1}{q}$ tenglik kelib chiqadi. Bu tenglikni

yuqoridagi tengsizlikga qo'ysak.

$$\sum_{i=1}^n m_i x_i \leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^n m_i \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n m_i x_i^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

$i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ uchun $m_i = b_i^q$ va $x_i = a_i b_i^{1-q}$ deb belgilash kiritsak. Biz

$$\sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i \leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n b_i^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}.$$

Gyolder tengsizligiga ega bo'lamiz.

Eslatma. Agar $p = q = 2$ bo'lsa Gyolder tengsizligidan Koshi-Bunyokovskiy tengsizligi kelib chiqadi.

Teorema.(Minkovskiyning ikkinchi tengsizligi) Agar $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n; b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n$ musbat haqiqiy sonlar va $p > 1$ sonlar uchun

$$\left(\left(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i \right)^p + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n b_i \right)^p \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \leq \sum_{i=1}^n (a_i^p + b_i^q)^{\frac{1}{q}}$$

tengsizli o'rinli va tenglik holadi faqat va faqat $\frac{a_1}{b_1} = \frac{a_2}{b_2} = \dots = \frac{a_n}{b_n}$ bo'lganda bo'ladi.

Isbot. Agar $f: \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+, f(x) = (1 + x^p)^{\frac{1}{p}}$ funksiya $p > 1$ da quyidan qat'iy qavariq chunki $f''(x) = (p-1)(x^{-p} + 1)^{\frac{1-2p}{p}} \cdot x^{-p-1} > 0$ ixtiyoriy $x \in \mathbb{R}^+$ va $p > 1$ lar uchun. Yensen tengsizligidan foydalansak.

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 7, 31 Июль

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(1 + \left(\frac{m_1 x_1 + m_2 x_2 + \dots + m_n x_n}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n} \right)^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \leq \frac{(m_1(1+x_1^p))^{\frac{1}{p}} + m_2(1+x_2^p)^{\frac{1}{p}} + \dots + m_n(1+x_n^p)^{\frac{1}{p}}}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n} \\ & \Leftrightarrow \left(\left(\sum_{i=1}^n m_i \right)^p + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n m_i x_i \right)^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \leq \sum_{i=1}^n ((m_i)^p + (m_i x_i)^p)^{\frac{1}{p}} \end{aligned}$$

Agar biz $i=1,2,\dots,n$ uchun $m_i = a_i$ va $x_i = \frac{b_i}{a_i}$ almashtirish bajarsak

$$\left(\left(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i \right)^p + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n b_i \right)^p \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \leq \sum_{i=1}^n (a_i^p + b_i^q)^{\frac{1}{q}}$$

tengsizliga ega bo'lamiz. Tengsizlik isbotlandi.

Teorema. (Minkovskiyning uchinchi tengsizligi)

Agar $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n; b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n$ musbat haqiqiy sonlar uchun

$$\sqrt[n]{a_1 a_2 \dots a_n} + \sqrt[n]{b_1 b_2 \dots b_n} \leq \sqrt[n]{(a_1 + b_1)(a_2 + b_2) \dots (a_n + b_n)}$$

tengsizlik o'rinli va tenglik holati faqat va faqat $\frac{a_1}{b_1} = \frac{a_2}{b_2} = \dots = \frac{a_n}{b_n}$ bo'lganda

barajiriladi.

Isbot. Agar $f(x) = \ln(1 + e^x)$ funksiyani $\mathbb{R}$ da quyidan qavariq chunki

$f''(x) = \frac{e^x}{(1+e^x)^2} > 0$ ixtiyoriy $x \in \mathbb{R}$ uchun. Yensin tengsizligidan foydalansak

$$f\left(\frac{m_1 x_1 + m_2 x_2 + \dots + m_n x_n}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}\right) \leq \frac{m_1 f(x_1) + m_2 f(x_2) + \dots + m_n f(x_n)}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}$$

tengsizlikda $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ uchun $m_i = \frac{1}{n}$ va $x_i = \ln \frac{b_i}{a_i}$ almashtirish bajaramiz.

$$\ln \left(1 + \exp \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \ln \frac{b_i}{a_i} \right) \right) \leq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \ln \left(1 + \exp \left(\ln \frac{b_i}{a_i} \right) \right)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \ln \left(1 + \prod_{i=1}^n \sqrt[n]{\frac{b_i}{a_i}} \right) \leq \frac{1}{n} \ln \prod_{i=1}^n \left(1 + \frac{b_i}{a_i} \right)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow 1 + \sqrt[n]{\frac{b_1 b_2 \dots b_n}{a_1 a_2 \dots a_n}} \leq \sqrt[n]{\left(1 + \frac{b_1}{a_1} \right) \left(1 + \frac{b_2}{a_2} \right) \dots \left(1 + \frac{b_n}{a_n} \right)}$$

tengsizlikning ikkala tomonini $\sqrt[n]{a_1 a_2 \dots a_n}$ ga ko'paytirsak

$$\sqrt[n]{a_1 a_2 \dots a_n} + \sqrt[n]{b_1 b_2 \dots b_n} \leq \sqrt[n]{(a_1 + b_1)(a_2 + b_2) \dots (a_n + b_n)}$$

tengsizlik kelib chiqadi. Minkovskiy tengsizligi isbotlandi.

5. Yensen tengsizligining tadbirlari.

1-misol. ABC uchburchakning α, β va γ burchaklari uchun quyidagi tengsizlikni isbotlang.

$$\sin \alpha \sin \beta \sin \gamma \leq \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{8}$$

Isbot. Bizga malumki $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in (0, \pi)$ va $\sin \alpha, \sin \beta, \sin \gamma > 0$ bo'ladi. U holda $AM - GM$ tengsizligidan foydalanib

$$\sqrt[3]{\sin \alpha \sin \beta \sin \gamma} \leq \frac{\sin \alpha + \sin \beta + \sin \gamma}{3}$$

ga ega bo'lamiz.

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 7, 31 Июль

Endi $f(x) = \sin x$ funksiya $(0, \pi)$ da yuqoridan qavariq chunki $f''(x) = -\sin x < 0$ bo'ladi barcha $x \in (0, \pi)$ uchun. Yensin tengsizligidan foydalanamiz.

$$\frac{\sin \alpha + \sin \beta + \sin \gamma}{3} \leq \sin \left(\frac{\alpha + \beta + \gamma}{3} \right) = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

U holda

$$\sqrt[3]{\sin \alpha \sin \beta \sin \gamma} \leq \frac{\sin \alpha + \sin \beta + \sin \gamma}{3} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \sin \alpha \sin \beta \sin \gamma \leq \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{8}$$

tengsizlik hosil bo'ladi. Tengsizlik isbotlandi.

2-misol. Agar $x > 0, y > 0, z > 0$ va $x + y + z = 1$ bo'lsa quyidagi tengsizlikni isbotlang.

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{y}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{z}\right) \geq 64$$

Isbot. Agar $f(t) = \ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{t}\right)$ funksiyaning $(0, \infty)$ sohada qarash. f funksiya quyidan qavariq chunki $f''(t) = \frac{1}{t^2} - \frac{1}{(1+t)^2} > 0$ bo'ladi ixtiyoriy $x \in (0, \infty)$ uchun. $n = 3$ holda Yensen tengsizlikini qo'llasak.

$$f(\lambda_1 x_1 + \lambda_2 x_2 + \lambda_3 x_3) \leq \lambda_1 f(x_1) + \lambda_2 f(x_2) + \lambda_3 f(x_3).$$

Agar $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \frac{1}{3}, x_1 = x, x_2 = y, x_3 = z$ deb belgilash kiritamiz

$$f\left(\frac{x}{3} + \frac{y}{3} + \frac{z}{3}\right) \leq \frac{1}{3}(f(x) + f(y) + f(z))$$

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 7, 31 Июль

$$\Leftrightarrow \ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right) + \ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{y}\right) + \ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{z}\right) \geq 3\ln\left(1 + \frac{3}{x+y+z}\right)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right)\left(1 + \frac{1}{y}\right)\left(1 + \frac{1}{z}\right) \geq 3\ln 4$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right)\left(1 + \frac{1}{y}\right)\left(1 + \frac{1}{z}\right) \geq 64$$

kelib chiqadi. Tengsizlik isbotlandi.

3-misol. $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n > 1$ haqiqiy sonlar uchun

$$(a_1 a_2 \dots a_n)^{\sqrt[n]{a_1 a_2 \dots a_n}} \leq a_1^{a_1} a_2^{a_2} \dots a_n^{a_n}$$

tengsizlikni isbotlang.

Isbot. Agar $f(x) = xe^x$ funksiya $(0, \infty)$ sohada qaraymiz. f funksiya quyidan qavariq chunki $f''(x) = 2e^x + xe^x > 0$ bo'ladi ixtiyoriy $x \in (0, \infty)$ uchun. Yensen tengsizligini qo'llaymiz.

$$f\left(\frac{m_1 x_1 + m_2 x_2 + \dots + m_n x_n}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}\right) \leq \frac{m_1 f(x_1) + m_2 f(x_2) + \dots + m_n f(x_n)}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}$$

Agar $m_1 = m_2 = \dots = m_n = 1$ deb belgilasak

$$f\left(\frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}\right) \leq \frac{f(x_1) + f(x_2) + \dots + f(x_n)}{n}.$$

$$\Leftrightarrow (x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n) e^{\frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}} \leq x_1 e^{x_1} + x_2 e^{x_2} + \dots + x_n e^{x_n}$$

Agar $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ uchun $x_i = \ln a_i$ deb belgilsh kiritsak va soddalashtirsak.

$$\ln(a_1 a_2 \dots a_n) e^{\frac{\ln(a_1 a_2 \dots a_n)}{n}} \leq a_1 \ln a_1 + a_2 \ln a_2 + \dots + a_n \ln a_n$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \ln(a_1 a_2 \dots a_n) (a_1 a_2 \dots a_n)^{\frac{1}{n}} \leq \ln(a_1^{a_1} a_2^{a_2} \dots a_n^{a_n})$$

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 7, 31 Июль

$$\Leftrightarrow (a_1 a_2 \dots a_n)^{\frac{1}{a_1 a_2 \dots a_n}} \leq a_1^{a_1} a_2^{a_2} \dots a_n^{a_n}$$

tengsizlik kelib chiqadi. Tengsizlik isbotlandi.

4-misol. Agar $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$ musbat haqiqiy sonlar bo'lsin u holda k ning qanday qiymatida quyidagi tengsizlik o'rinli bo'ladi. (bu yerda k soni n ga bog'liq)

$$\sqrt[n]{a_1} + \sqrt[n]{a_2} \dots + \sqrt[n]{a_n} \leq k \sqrt[n]{a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n}$$

Yechish. Agar $f: \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, f(x) = x^p$ funsiya $0 < p < 1$ uchun qaraymiz. $f(x)$ funsiya yuqoridan qavariq chunki $f''(x) = p(p-1)x^{p-2} < 0$ bo'ladi. U xolda Yensen tengsizligini qo'llasak.

$$\left(\frac{m_1 x_1 + m_2 x_2 + \dots + m_n x_n}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n} \right)^p \geq \frac{m_1 x_1^p + m_2 x_2^p + \dots + m_n x_n^p}{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}$$

yoki biroz soddalashtirsak

$$(m_1 x_1 + m_2 x_2 + \dots + m_n x_n)^p \geq (m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n)^{p-1} (m_1 x_1^p + m_2 x_2^p + \dots + m_n x_n^p)$$

ko'rinishga keladi. Agar $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ uchun $x_i = a_i$, $m_1 = m_2 = \dots = m_n = \frac{1}{n}$, va

$$p = \frac{1}{n}$$

deb belgilash kiritsak

$$\left(\frac{a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n}{n} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \geq \frac{a_1^{\frac{1}{n}} + a_2^{\frac{1}{n}} + \dots + a_n^{\frac{1}{n}}}{n}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \sqrt[n]{a_1} + \sqrt[n]{a_2} \dots + \sqrt[n]{a_n} \leq n^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \sqrt[n]{a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n}$$

bo'ladi. Demak $k = n^{\frac{n-1}{n}}$ ekan.

ADABIYOTLAR:

**МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ:
ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА**

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 7, 31 Июль

1. G.Xudayberganov, A.K.Vorisov, X.T.Mansurov, B.A.Shoimqulov.
Matematika analiz

fanidan ma'ruzalar, 1-qism. "Vorish-nashriyoti", Toshkent -2010.

2. T.Azlarov, X.Mansurov. Matematika analiz, 1-qism. Toshkent-1995.

3. Zdravko Cvetkovski, "Inequalities", Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg 2012.

4. Sh. Ismailov, O. Ibrogimov. Tengsizliklar-II. Isbotlashning zamonaviy
usullari,

Toshkent, 2008 y.

5. Hayk Sedrakyan, Nairi Sedrakyan, Algebraic Inequalities, Springer
International Publishing AG, part of Springer Nature 2018.